

COMPUTATIONAL MODELLING OF DRUG-COATED BALLOONS IMPLANTED IN ARTERIES WITH HETEROGENEOUS TISSUE COMPOSITION: ASSESSMENT OF VESSEL PRE-DILATION INFLUENCE ON DRUG DELIVERY PARAMETERS

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The present research work aims to develop a computational model capable of simulating drug-coated delivery to arteries of heterogeneous tissue composition to optimize drug delivery parameters. Drug-coated balloon (DCB) therapy has recently emerged as an appealing non-stent-based strategy for the treatment of arterial lesions in obstructive arterial disease. However, the delivery of the antiproliferative drugs into the arterial wall during balloon inflation is still inefficient. Within this scenario, in-silico modelling is a potential tool for improving the drug delivery efficacy, which is highly dependent on the heterogeneous tissue composition and the effects of vessel pre-dilation using a common angioplasty balloon before DCB inflation. This work aims to develop a 3D finite element model of atherosclerotic artery pre-dilation to provide an effective means of simulating DCB treatment and drug delivery in near future steps. The inflation of a tri-folded balloon in a 3-layered structure artery with atherosclerotic plaque in the mid-section is simulated by using Abaqus. The artery wall is described as highly deformable, hyperelastic, and nearly incompressible material and different constitutive models for the artery material behaviour are assessed. A cohesive zone model (CZM) approach is applied by placing cohesive elements along the plaque-media interface to simulate plaque delamination induced by angioplasty treatment. The proposed approach is intended to be the first step toward a patient-specific numerical tool able to incorporate the effects of the arterial damage induced by balloon angioplasty on the subsequent DCB treatment to optimize the drug delivery to the pre-dilated artery.

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